

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

Factors influencing the choice of Long-Term Contraceptive Methods (LTCM) among family planning acceptors: A literature review

Rizkita Nur Azizah *

Department of Epidemiology, Biostatistics, Population and Health Promotion, Faculty of Public Health, Airlangga University, Surabaya, Indonesia.

World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2023, 20(02), 071–075

Publication history: Received on 16 September 2023; revised on 28 October 2023; accepted on 30 October 2023

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2023.20.2.2182>

Abstract

Long-term contraceptive methods refer to contraception that can be used for an extended period, exceeding two years. Many family planning acceptors prefer non-long-term contraceptive methods due to their practicality. The aim of this study is to identify the factors influencing the choice of long-term contraceptive methods among family planning acceptors. The study design is a literature review. Articles selected through Google Scholar's correlation articles with respondents were included. Inclusion criteria for the chosen articles were thematic relevance, family planning acceptors population, and scholarly articles published from 2018 to 2023. The results analyzed by the researcher it can be concluded that several factors significantly influence the selection of Long-Term Contraceptive Methods (LTCM) among family planning acceptors. The most dominant factor is knowledge, followed by other factors such as spousal support, age, number of children, personal attitudes and experiences, sociocultural factors, healthcare accessibility, as well as income and occupation.

Keywords: Long-Term Contraceptive Methods; Influence Factor; Family Plan Acceptors

1. Introduction

Good public health is one of the keys to the formation of prosperity in society. Reproductive health is one of the aspects that must be prioritized in upholding public health because it is related to fertility and mortality rates among mothers and children. Reproductive health plays a crucial role in controlling population growth, therefore numerous reproductive health programs have been established in Indonesia.

Reproductive health programs are expected to improve the health and well-being of mothers, children, families, and the nation, reduce birth rates to enhance the standard of living for the people and the nation, and provide quality reproductive health services, including efforts to reduce maternal, infant, and child mortality rates as well as addressing reproductive health issues [8].

One such program is Family Planning, which broadly refers to an effort to regulate pregnancies in a way that positively impacts the mother, baby, father, and their respective families, avoiding any direct negative consequences resulting from these pregnancies [9]. One of the methods used to regulate pregnancies is the use of contraceptives. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), contraception is an action that assists individuals or couples in achieving specific objectives: preventing unwanted births, having desired births, regulating the intervals between pregnancies, and controlling the timing of births within marital relationships [8].

Contraceptive methods are divided into two categories based on their duration of use, namely short-term contraceptive methods and long-term contraceptive methods (LTCM). LTCM can be used for an extended period, exceeding two years,

* Corresponding author: Rizkita Nur Azizah

offering numerous advantages both programmatically and for clients. Additionally, LTCM can significantly contribute to reducing the Total Fertility Rate (TFR) due to their high effectiveness in preventing pregnancies. LTCM include implants, intrauterine devices (IUDs), male and female permanent contraception methods [5].

The trend in LTCM usage shows a natural situation where the percentage of LTCM users increases with the age of family planning service users. However, this increase is not significant. In reality, the percentage of injection and pill contraceptive users among older age groups remains relatively high (>60%) for those aged 45-49 years, and even higher for younger age groups. When associated with the goals of contraceptive use and its effectiveness, this trend does not paint a positive picture because a significant portion of family planning participants still rely on short-term contraception methods [9].

Reducing maternal mortality rates will be achieved by increasing the continuity of participation in family planning programs. Long-term contraceptive methods (LTCM) are the most effective family planning methods in increasing this continuity. The use of LTCM by Couples of Reproductive Age (CRA) is influenced by various factors, including the quality and accessibility of family planning services, limited resources, provider competence, and knowledge. These limitations often force prospective family planning acceptors to opt for non-LTCM methods, which are perceived as more practical [10]. Based on the aforementioned background, this research aims to identify the factors influencing the choice of long-term contraceptive methods among family planning acceptors.

2. Material and methods

This study falls under qualitative research, employing a literature review method with a descriptive-analytical approach. The data for this study were sourced from national scientific journal articles obtained through Google Scholar using the keywords "influence factor," "LTCM," and "family planning acceptors." Inclusion criteria for this research were titles corresponding to the research theme, namely factors influencing the choice of long-term contraceptive methods, with the study population being family planning acceptors, and scholarly articles published from 2018 to 2023 (the last five years). Relevant research articles were identified using a literature review method, comparing articles with similarities in their research, particularly those related to the factors influencing the choice of contraceptive methods among family planning acceptors.

3. Results and discussion

Based on the collected and analyzed articles, the findings are presented as follows:

Table 1 List of Articles

No.	Author	Method	Result
1	Anggraeni NS et al.	Case-control	The research findings mention that age ($p=0.000$), parity ($p=0.013$), access to healthcare services (0.005), and spousal support ($p=0.017$) are significantly related factors affecting the choice of long-term contraceptive methods in the Bandorasa Kulon Village, Cilimus District, Kuningan Regency.
2	Ariesta and Fitra	Survey analytic	A study conducted in the Kuala Lumpur Village under the jurisdiction of the Simalinyang Public Health Center demonstrates that good knowledge ($p=0.027$), spousal support ($p=0.000$), and parity ($p=0.002$) are influencing factors in family planning acceptors' choice of long-term contraceptive methods.
3	Hasibuan R et al.	Cross-sectional	In the research conducted at the Purwosari Public Health Center in Surakarta City, it was revealed that having achieved the desired number of children ($p=0.012$), spousal support ($p=0.045$), and experiencing no side effects ($p=0.001$) are tendencies among family planning acceptors to choose long-term contraceptive methods.
4	Hastuty and Afiah	Cross-sectional	Significant factors influencing the selection of long-term contraceptive methods among family planning acceptors at the Tambang Public Health Center are age ($p=0.001$), education ($p=0.001$), and knowledge ($p=0.027$).

5	Jasa NE et al.	Cross-sectional	At the PMB Rosbiatul facility, significant factors related to the selection of long-term contraceptive methods include parity among family planning acceptors ($p=0.003$), higher education ($p=0.002$), and occupation type ($p=0.003$).
6	Kurrohman T	Case-control	In the study involving active family planning acceptors in the Air Bara Public Health Center area, South Bangka Regency, the factors significantly related to the low selection of long-term contraceptive methods are knowledge ($p=0.028$), attitude ($p=0.015$), income ($p=0.005$), information sources ($p=0.002$), and spousal support ($p=0.036$), with information sources being the dominant factor.
7	Laurensi and Mustikawati	Case-control	At the Cengkareng Public Health Center, a higher education level ($p=0.001$), good knowledge ($p=0.006$), and support from partners ($p=0.005$) are significant factors related to the use of long-term contraceptive methods.
8	Rismawati et al.	Cross-sectional	Good knowledge ($p=0.033$) and favorable attitudes of respondents ($p=0.008$) toward long-term contraceptive methods based on personal experiences, social influence, cultural factors, and social media are significant factors influencing the selection of long-term contraceptive methods at the Mayor Umar Damanik Public Health Center.
9	Suryanti, Yuli	Cross-sectional	The research results indicate that good knowledge ($p=0.000$), young age ($p=0.000$), and spousal support ($p=0.000$) are significant factors influencing the utilization of long-term contraceptives among family planning acceptors at the Paal V Public Health Center.

Based on the identification through the 9 articles listed in the table, several factors influence the selection of Long-Term Contraceptive Methods (LTCM) among family planning acceptors.

- Influence of Knowledge on the Selection of Long-Term Contraceptive Methods (LTCM) among Family Planning Acceptors:
- Knowledge in this context includes respondents' understanding of long-term contraceptive methods, including types, purposes, benefits, advantages, and side effects of long-term contraceptives. Based on the research results, it can be concluded that most respondents have good knowledge about LTCM [2]. According to the research findings, family planning acceptors' knowledge is closely related to the choice of contraceptives. Good knowledge about specific contraceptive methods changes acceptors' perspectives, enabling them to choose the most suitable and effective contraception. This knowledge helps users feel comfortable with their chosen method and prevents errors in selecting the most suitable contraceptive for themselves [8].
- Influence of Husband's Support on the Selection of Long-Term Contraceptive Methods (LTCM) among Family Planning Acceptors:
- The husband's support plays a significant role for a wife in making decisions, including decisions about contraception. Spousal approval is the most crucial factor because husbands are seen as protectors, breadwinners, and decision-makers. Therefore, wives who receive support from their husbands in choosing contraceptives tend to use the contraceptive methods preferred by their husbands out of respect and trust in their decisions [7].
- Influence of Age on the Selection of Long-Term Contraceptive Methods (LTCM) among Family Planning Acceptors:
- Age is one of the factors influencing an individual's behavior in using contraceptives. Older individuals have a smaller chance of using contraceptives compared to younger ones [9]. Family planning acceptors aged 20-30 years tend to choose short-term contraceptive methods because they feel they are too young for long-term contraceptive methods (LTCM). For respondents aged 20-30, this age period is considered ideal for childbirth, with two children and a birth spacing of 2 to 4 years. In contrast, respondents over 30 choose long-term contraceptive methods (LTCM) because they feel they are too old to have more children, especially due to the health risks associated with childbirth after the age of 30. The period for respondents over 30, especially above 35 years, typically marks the end of fertility, especially after having two children [1].
- Influence of Parity on the Selection of Long-Term Contraceptive Methods (LTCM) among Family Planning Acceptors:
- The number of children or parity of family planning acceptors also influences the choice of LTCM. Mothers who have two or more children tend to be interested in stopping childbirth, especially if the mother's age is at a high risk for complications during pregnancy and childbirth. Therefore, choosing LTCM is very appropriate, as its

success rate is higher compared to non-LTCM. Thus, midwives or healthcare providers need to provide accurate and complete information about LTCM [5].

- Influence of Attitude on the Selection of Long-Term Contraceptive Methods (LTCM) among Family Planning Acceptors:
- One of the internal factors of family planning acceptors that affects the selection of long-term contraceptive methods is attitude. Family planning acceptors' attitudes about LTCM are influenced by several factors, including personal experience, influence from important people, cultural influence, and mass media influence. These experiences can include understanding LTCM, side effects of LTCM, types of LTCM, and people's attitudes towards using LTCM. Family planning acceptors' experiences, especially regarding attitudes about using LTCM, are one of the sources or references for respondents in responding to the use of LTCM [8].
- Influence of Socio-Cultural Factors on the Selection of Long-Term Contraceptive Methods (LTCM) among Family Planning Acceptors:
- Related to family planning acceptors' attitudes, experiences, and socio-cultural influence also determine the use of LTCM. The research results show that the majority of respondents (LTCM family planning acceptors) stopped using contraception mostly due to experiencing side effects. However, family planning authorities explain that the side effects of using LTCM are the same as when using non-LTCM, namely irregular periods and increased menstrual bleeding. The most common side effects they experience are longer menstrual periods and heavier menstrual bleeding [3].
- Influence of Access to Healthcare Services on the Selection of Long-Term Contraceptive Methods (LTCM) among Family Planning Acceptors:
- In using contraception, family planning acceptors also consider access to healthcare services, including distance, time, and ease of transportation. Regardless, varying regions, diverse transportation, and difficult areas are essential factors in gaining access to family planning services, especially in rural areas [1].
- Influence of Income and Occupation on the Selection of Long-Term Contraceptive Methods (LTCM) among Family Planning Acceptors:
- Income and type of occupation are further factors that influence the choice of LTCM among family planning acceptors. Women with better incomes tend to choose more expensive contraceptive methods and find it easier to make choices without strict rules requiring spousal approval. Additionally, by working, a mother will have broader insights and social interactions, allowing her to obtain more information and easily choose a more effective and efficient contraceptive method [5].

4. Conclusion

Based on the identification from the 9 analyzed articles, the selection of Long-Term Contraceptive Methods (LTCM) among family planning acceptors is influenced by several complex factors, including good knowledge about LTCM, spousal support, age, number of children, attitudes, and personal experiences, socio-cultural factors, access to healthcare services, as well as income and occupation. This conclusion emphasizes the importance of a holistic approach in reproductive health programs to understand and meet the needs and preferences of individuals in choosing suitable contraceptive methods.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgements

This article did not receive assistance from the government, private companies, or non-profit organizations.

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